

Hormesis

The Arndt-Schulz law rediscovered

by Karl Robinson, USA

The Arndt-Schulz law which states that biological systems respond very differently to chemicals in different doses has been rediscovered by research biologists and renamed hormesis. Much new experimental evidence has been accumulated over the last forty years showing that biological, physiological or biochemical responses to a drug at a low dose may be completely opposite to that response when a larger dose is administered. This paper reports on some of that research which is thought to buttress homeopathic theory.

The Arndt-Schulz Law, which used to be mentioned in every complete course on homeopathy, was formulated by Arndt in 1888 and restated by Hueppe a few years later. It states: **For every substance, small doses stimulate, moderate doses inhibit, large doses kill.**

Modern pharmacology has traditionally taught that very low concentrations of medicines have little or no effect on living organisms. As a result experiments using low doses of pharmacological substances have not been done. Pharmacology strives to determine the LD 50 - that dose is lethal to 50% of the test animals - and then reduce the dosage from there to that level which inhibits various biochemical and physiological functions without causing too many undesirable adverse reactions. That dosage, usually measured in milligrams, has been found to be most useful in pharmacological medicine.

Homeopaths have traditionally been interested not only in small doses of various medicinal substances but small doses which have been serially diluted and succussed. Though there has been promising research in the last five years using homeopathic medicines in humans and animals the amount of such research has been disappointingly small.

As early as the 1940's in the fields of radiation and toxicology research some theretofore inexplicable phenomena were being observed. Certain toxins in high doses were inhibiting metabolism and ultimately causing death, an understandable and expected result. But at low doses they produced a stimulatory effect. This was totally unexpected and not explainable by biological scientists. As the evidence accumulated, the phenomenon acquired a new name, hormesis, which refers to a biphasic dose-response relationship in which higher doses cause an inhibitory and lower doses cause a stimulatory effect.

So vast has been the experimental data supporting hormesis that the Conference on Radiation Hormesis was held in California in 1985 and was attended by 158 scientists from several countries including the Peoples Republic of China. It brought together and assessed current scientific information in the fields of general hormesis phenomenology (as related to chemical and physical agents) as well as hormesis from ionizing radiation. Of the 36 papers presented, 22 were published in *Health Physics*, Vol. 52, Nr. 5 (May 1987). Several of the more interesting papers will be summarized.

Egon Lorenz in the early 1940's did experiments on the effects of chronic low level ionizing radiation on mice and guinea pigs. Observations on life span, body weight and radiation carcinogenesis were tabulated on both species exposed to 0.11 R per 8 hour a day until natural death. Irradiated animals had a slightly greater mean life span than control animals. In addition there was a marked weight gain during the growth phase in both species irradiated. Increased tumor incidence, as might be expected, was also observed at the 0.1 R level in mice. Nevertheless, the irradiated mice outlived those that received no ionizing radiation (1). George Sacher, commenting on the mean life-lengthening effect, wrote "(...) this effect is due to an as yet unexplained action of small repeated dosages, which leads to a decreased rate of mortality from infectious disease. We have confirmed the existence of this effect and have it under further study at present" (2).

In a study using Phosfon, a known synthetic growth retardant in plants, opposite effects in growth were observed depending on the dosage. Phosfon was exposed to peppermint, (*Mentha piperita*). The aim was to make plants shorter, more compact and possibly more attrac-

tive for commercial purpose. Though it did just that at higher doses, at lower doses it caused an unexpected apparent stimulation in growth. The researchers replicated these results on numerous occasions in both hydroponic and soil media with very similar results. This biphasic dose-response relationship for Phosfon with peppermint was found to hold in experiments with zinnias and morning glories (3).

In another study the reproductive life span of female Sprague-Dawley rats was studied. Female rats exposed to 20 ppm (parts per million) DDT in their food from 3 weeks of age to the end of their lives had a significantly longer reproductive life span of 14.55 months when compared to their litter-mate controls of 8.5 months. Although average litter size and viability of the young did not differ significantly between the two groups the DDT exposed animals had a higher number of successful late life pregnancies than did the controls (3).

The authors concluded that "...hormesis occurs broadly in the plant and animal kingdoms for a wide range of agents and biological end points...". They further commented, "Thus, since much of the toxicological research and/or testing taking place in the United States is driven by regulatory concern and conformity with approved government-mandated testing protocols, there is little opportunity to search for broad dose response relationships which cover a number of orders of magnitude of dose" (3).

In a study done in China the authors commented on the health effects of low level radiation in an area of high natural radioactivity in the Guangdong Province. The annual dose equivalent in this area is about three times as high as that of the control area. Studies on the immune status of the inhabitants revealed a defi-

nite increase in reactivity of T lymphocytes to phytohemagglutinin (PHA), a slight increase in the percentage of B lymphocytes and a tendency toward enhancement of unscheduled DNA synthesis in peripheral blood lymphocytes in the inhabitants of the high natural radioactivity area. The authors wrote, "These findings suggest there might be a stimulatory effect of low level radiation on the defense mechanisms of the human body" (4).

The authors then ran experiments with mouse splenocytes which showed that after small doses of both single and continuous irradiation with x or gamma rays the splenocytes showed increased capacity of DNA repair synthesis following UV radiation damage.

The authors concluded, "It is speculated from data of human studies and animal experiments that under certain circumstances the immune system might be stimulated by low level ionizing radiation, enhancing the body's defense mechanism as a whole" (4).

In the May 1987 issue of *Health Physics* Leonard A. Sagan of the Electric Power Institute of Palo Alto, California noted that all areas of science make "sets of assumptions regarding the operation of complex systems." One set of assumptions "...states that biological observations at high doses can be used to predict effects at low doses. Because significant effects can be detected only at high doses, and because most biological systems are

overwhelmed at high doses, harmful effects consistently occur. Thus our assessment of the influence of most environmental agents at low doses is strongly coloured by the poisonous consequences of high dose exposures" (5).

The radiation paradigm is a case in point. It states, writes Sagan, "...that 1) radiation exposure is harmful; 2) radiation exposure is harmful at all dose levels; 3) there are no effects at low doses which cannot be predicted from effects noted at high-dose levels" (5). But the studies of Lorenz, (1) suggest this paradigm is inaccurate, that low doses of ionizing radiation stimulate biological systems even though high doses are lethal. Clearly, vitamins, minerals, sunlight and hormones all of which are naturally occurring can be either indispensable for life or life threatening. Their life sustaining properties are dose related and their life threatening properties are just as dose related. Nickel and chromium are both necessary to nutrition in physiological doses. In high doses both are known carcinogens. The same has been proved true for female sex hormones.

Arthur Furst noted that certain arsenic compounds in small doses when mixed in the food of certain domestic animals will stimulate growth. "At much higher levels," he wrote, "the growth rate is retarded. Here, arsenic acts as a growth promoter and may be essential in small amounts for these animals. At higher levels the toxicity

of arsenic is clearly evident" (6).

Nickel, the element, has been known to induce cancer. It is also known to be an essential trace element for avian species (6). Nielsen found that trace amounts of nickel in the food supply are necessary for the chick to grow. At higher doses the hometic effect of nickel comes into play and nickel is toxic (7).

It is ironic that such a significant body of research partially validating homeopathic principles should be virtually unknown to most practising homeopaths. It was not until January of this year that I stumbled on the term *hormesis* while preparing a lecture for homeopathic students on research. I had never heard of *hormesis* before and was delighted that so many high quality experiments had been performed which validated the old *Amdt-Schulz Law*. It is my belief that we homeopaths need to be conversant with the literature on *hormesis* for it is entirely consistent with what we are about. Unfortunately, workers in the field of *hormesis* have not performed experiments using diluted and succussed substances. Nevertheless, the fact that they have proved that "the great majority of natural agents do not behave in a linear fashion" (6), can be invaluable to us as we seek greater acceptance of homeopathic ideas. ☐

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"Now, lets lower the sales and measure his stress symptoms ..."

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